

Between history and cultural psychology: Some reflections on mediation and normativity when reconstructing the past

Ignacio Brescó de Luna (Aalborg University)

Department of Communication and Psychology, Niels Bohr Centre for Cultural Psychology, Kroghstræde 3, 9220 Aalborg, Denmark.

Email: ignacio@hum.aau.dk

Abstract

Innis' and Brinkmann's papers tackle two key aspects in cultural psychology: the mediating role played by the different systems of meanings throughout history in making sense of the world, and the normative role of those systems, including psychology itself. This paper offers a reflection on these two issues. It begins by highlighting the contribution of psychology and history, as emerging disciplines in the 19th century, to the creation of a normative framework for the subject of modernity according to the needs of modern nation states. It also alludes to both disciplines' common pursuit of a reference point in natural science in order to achieve a status that is on a par with the latter's. It is argued that this resulted in an objectivist stance that equates the study of memory and history with an accurate reproduction of the past, thus concealing the mediated nature of past accounts. Drawing on this assumption, it is discussed how past events are constructed, thus bringing mediation and meaning-making to the fore. Special attention is paid to narratives as symbolic meaning-making tools. We will conclude by discussing usage of the past and the role that cultural psychology can play in this field.

Keywords

Mediation, normative framework, memory, history, narratives, past events

Introduction

“It is not expected of critics as it is of poets that they should help us to make sense of our lives; they are bound only to attempt the lesser feat of making sense of the ways we try to make sense of our lives” (Kermode, 1966, p. 3)

Both Brinkmann’s (2016) and Innis’ (2016) articles tackle two key issues in cultural psychology. On the one hand, there is the mediating role played by the different systems of meaning throughout history when it comes to making sense of the world and of ourselves. On the other, there is the regulatory and normative role of those systems, including psychology itself, insofar as they have given rise to different anthropological models in light of which human experience and behaviour have been studied, interpreted and evaluated.

As regard the idea of mediation, Innis (2016) highlights the link between cultural psychology and philosophical semiotics in their common pursuit of “mak[ing] sense of how human beings make sense of themselves and the world and the tools and instruments employed, no matter what their modality is” (p. 3). This idea goes back in psychology to Vygotsky (1987), who argued that human beings actively manipulate their environment by means of different physical or symbolic tools. In this way, whilst physical tools externally mediate man’s relationship with his environment for the purpose of controlling the latter, symbolic tools such as language are internally oriented, mediating man’s relationship with himself and others in order to regulate his conduct. Wertsch (2006) states that “to be human is to use the cultural tools, or mediational means, that are provided by a particular socio-cultural setting” (p. 11). The use and development of such artifacts, particularly those of a symbolic nature, has enabled humans to surpass purely biological limits and thus expand their psychological functions, which leads to new forms of experience and behaviour (Vygotsky, 1987). Symbolic mediation of human experience results from a wide array of cultural creations (myths, religion, science, art, history, etc.), which shape the way we make sense of the world and ourselves. According to Rosa (2007), this symbolic mediation has an intrinsic poetic dimension (from the Greek verb *poieo*, which means construction and provides the root of the word poetry) inasmuch as our construction of reality is based upon different symbolic forms – an observation that echoes a philosophical tradition dating

back to Giambattista Vico, Friedrich Nietzsche, Ernst Cassirer and Suzanne Langer (Gibbs, 1994).

However, the sociocultural construction of reality inevitably generates a normative dimension as well, a set of value-laden models conveying proper ways to act for individuals and societies (Brinkmann, 2016), and this is also relevant in cultural psychology. As Innis (2016) puts it, this results in the study of “the multiform psychological reality and consequences of our world-pictures or world-models which shape and form our self-conceptions, our pictures of ourselves and what we want to be, [...] can be” (p. 5), and I would add, ought to be. In this respect, Brinkmann (2016) reminds us that “[p]sychology is [...] perhaps the most important picture-maker of humans today” (p. 3). Consequently, psychology is normative, since “[i]t constantly fabricates new ideas and images of human beings, which are put to use in various social practices, giving rise to many different effects” (Brinkmann, 2016, p. 3). Along these lines, different authors have studied the emerging role of Psychology in the mid-19th century, looking at how the tools provided by this discipline, whether in the form of discourses, technologies or institutions, have contributed to the construction of modern subjectivity vis-à-vis the demands of modern nation states (Rose, 1985), including the entrenchment of a collective sense of identity (Castro, Lafuente, & Jiménez, 2009). To that end, different psychological concepts and categories were used in order to imagine the cultural and psychological character of these national communities (Anderson, 1983).¹ As Castro and Rosa (2007) point out, “the goal was to underpin and harmonize the cultural framework of the new nation-states” (p. 72). This was a task that commenced within a psycho-pedagogical context which, along with the process of education for literacy, also played a decisive role in providing, via the teaching of history, the necessary symbolic tools for people to imagine a shared past, and therefore, a collective identity (Castro & Rosa, 2007).

Thus, almost in parallel to psychology, history, as an emerging discipline in the 19th century, contributed the symbolic tools to create the notion of a national subject (Hobsbawm, 1990). This is a notion that has become taken

¹ It is significant that the first chair with the term “psychology”, occupied by Lazarus at Bern in 1860, held the name of *Volkerpsychologie* (Jahoda, 1992).

for granted over the years, even considered as something banal (Billig, 1995), an aspect of people's common sense and nature to the point that, as Gellner (1983) states, "a man must have a nationality as he must have a nose and two ears" (p. 6). In that sense, the national reconstruction of the past has had a clear normative impact on both the very concept of identity and on the ways of understanding and navigating certain situations. Thus, assuming national accounts in the first person plural has fostered the internalisation of a certain grammar of motives (Burke, 1969) that has, in some circumstances, led people to sacrifice themselves, or to justify the sacrifice of others, for the sake of the nation. Furthermore, history, besides its role in the construction of subjects' identity, shares with psychology the pursuit of a reference point in natural science in order to achieve a status that is on a par with the latter's. That is why the birth of modern historiography is usually associated with the positivist viewpoint held by Leopold von Ranke, according to which historical accounts should merely show how the past actually was (*wie es eigentlich gewesen*).² This objectivist stance, shared by the classical approach which, since the works of Ebbinghaus, has dominated in psychology, and which tends to equate the study of the memory with an accurate reproduction of the past, refers to another normative dimension in relation to the psychology pointed out by Brinkmann (2016): "psychology is normative in a different way as well, having to do not so much with its effects as with its subject matter as such" (p. 4, emphasis in the original). For instance, the very manner in which memory is conceived would, in turn, imply adopting an evaluative background by virtue of which the memory would be studied and evaluated. More specifically, conceiving memory as a reproduction of the past (as it actually was) would lead to regarding accuracy as a virtue opposed to distortion or forgetting, which would form part of the so-called sins of memory (Schacter, 2001).

Nevertheless, the understanding of memory has changed throughout history, depending on the demands of each context, giving rise to what Danziger (2008) calls mnemonic values, i.e. values that imprint a normative dimension on the process of remembering, indicating what should be remembered and how it

² Leopold von Ranke used this expression in his 1821 lecture to the Prussian Academy of Sciences under the title Wilhelm von Humboldt: 'On the Historian's Task'. This lecture can be found in Iggers and von Moltke (1973).

should be remembered.³ In this respect, the notion of memory (and history), understood as an accurate reproduction of the past, has tended to conceal, among other aspects,⁴ the mediated and constructed nature of past accounts, and particularly, the mediational role of narratives as symbolic meaning-making tools. Drawing on this assumption, the following pages will provide a brief reflection on how accounts of the past are constructed, thus bringing mediation and meaning-making to the fore. Special attention will be paid to narratives and their role in the construction of past events, something that will bring us closer to the so-called narrative turn occurring in Human Sciences (Polkinghorne, 1988), and particularly in the areas that focus on the study of the past, such as history (Roberts, 2001) and psychology (Brockmeier & Harré, 2001). We will conclude by briefly discussing usage of the past, and therefore, the ethical dimensions of memory (Margalit, 2002), thus taking up Innis' (2016) concern regarding the role of cultural psychology, in this particular case, its role vis-à-vis how societies make sense of the past – an issue that, not insignificantly, runs in parallel to the crisis of the nation-states (Rosa & Brescó, forthcoming).

The mediated nature of past accounts

“No meaning resides in the events themselves. Indeed, until the historian decides on his area of inquiry and begins to create discrete units from the changing process in time, ‘events’ themselves do not exist.” (Egan, 1978, p. 82)

Both history and studies on memory in psychology have traditionally been influenced by a realist viewpoint in respect of the ways in which the past is represented. In line with Ranke's famous statement, this viewpoint has implied

³ See also Weinrich's work (2004) on the value of the art of forgetting in Western culture.

⁴ Somehow responding to Schacter's (2001) book on the seven sins of memory, Brown and Reavey (2015) put forward what they call the seven virtues of vital memory, thus highlighting the role of different aspects, some of them traditionally neglected by the main-stream approach to this topic: autobiography, agency, forgetting, ethics, affect, space and institutional practices.

evaluating both memories and historical accounts in accordance with their supposed correspondence with the past as it actually was. Brockmeier and Harré (2001) refer to such a viewpoint as representation fallacy, which consists of “supposing that there is one and only one human reality to which all narratives must in the end conform” (p. 48). According to this fallacy, past events are real entities, endowed with their own meaning, which is waiting, as it were, to be recovered and accurately mirrored in a narrative.

This perspective reminds us what Dewey called the spectator theory of knowledge, broached by Innis in his paper, inasmuch as the individual would assume a passive role, his or her goals, conceptions or problems being irrelevant when reconstructing the past. In fact, Dewey applied his critique of the spectator theory of knowledge to the work of historians in a short piece of writing entitled *Judgments recognized to be historical*, included in his *Logic: The Theory of Inquiry* (1938/1986) (see Hutt, 2013). In line with his anti-representationalist and pragmatist standpoint, Dewey contended that existential propositions like “x existed” or “y was a fact” result from a previous selection by historians according to their conceptions and specific inquiries (Hutt, 2013, p. 29). Dewey’s challenge to the Rankean tradition can be clearly perceived in the following quote:

“The statement ‘It actually happened in this way’ has its status and significance within the scope and perspective of historical writing. It does not determine the logical conditions of historical propositions, much less the identity of these propositions with events in their original occurrence.” (Dewey, 1938/1986, p. 237, in Hutt, 2013, p. 29)

Giving an account of the past does not therefore consist of representing, by means of language, the events that have supposedly been stored in either the historian’s files or in the individual’s mind; rather, the subject is required to adopt relevance or significance-based selection criteria for picking events out of the past. These criteria, based on the impact of past events on the present or future, in turn calls for the establishment of a storyline, as well as a theme on the basis of which to select, relate and significantly interpret the facts. In that regard, as the philosopher of history Arthur Danto (1985) observed, when someone says ‘tell me what happened, and do not leave anything out’, what

they mean is: 'I want you to tell me everything that forms part of the narrative'. Basically, enquiring into the significance of an event is asking something that can only be answered within the context of a narrative (Danto, 1985).⁵

In view of this, Danto suggests an abductive relationship – à la Peirce – between narratives and past events. Thus, past accounts, on the one hand, are supposed to be based on what remains of the past in the present such as documents, archaeological remains, witnesses, etc. On the other hand, however, the narrative dimension imposed on the past (such as the plot, the subject matter, the genre, etc.) becomes the criterion that leads the historian to select, interpret, appraise and even infer facts in such a way that they can be fitted into a certain storyline. Narratives and events of the past, far from being respectively regarded as “mere (verbalized) cop[ies] of (non-narrated) things [belonging to] the pre-symbolic world” (Bruner & Feldman, 1996, p. 293), are mediational tools through which events can be symbolically constructed and endowed with meaning. Past events would not be, then, pre-existing entities waiting to be represented by means of narratives; rather, they would be narrative entities themselves (see Brescó, 2008). In this line, Mink (1978), another philosopher of history, observes: “we cannot refer to events as such, but only to events under a description; so there can be more than one description of the same event” (p. 145). However, he raises the question as to “what can we possibly mean by ‘same event?’ Under what description do we refer to the event that is supposed to sustain different descriptions?” (p. 145). Mink concludes by saying that “events [...] are not the raw material out of which narratives are constructed; rather, an event is an abstraction from a narrative” (p. 147).

In sum, the past does not have its own voice; rather, it is endowed with meaning via different narrative forms, which inevitably convey a certain moral content – referred to by Hayden White (1986) as the content of the form. As White (1973) points out, historians emplot events of the past by turning to certain documents whilst ignoring others. The outcome is a version of the facts which usually takes on the appearance of a narrative structure with a

⁵ We can see a similar view in Ricoeur (1981) when he states that “to be historical, an event must be more than a singular occurrence, a unique happening. It receives its definition from its contribution to the development of a plot” (p. 167).

discernible beginning, middle and end. This implies a poetic act on the part of the historian, “poetic insofar as it is constitutive of the structure that will subsequently be imaged in the verbal model offered by the historian as a representation and explanation of ‘what really happened’ in the past” (White, 1973, p. 30). In that regard, as held by Kermode (1966), the problem arises when we end up assigning the properties of the narratives to reality, thus transforming historical accounts into myths that end up influencing our way of seeing the world and conducting ourselves within it. Nevertheless, White (1978), when underscoring the poetic nature of historical accounts, points out that this should not imply debasing historiography to the category of propaganda; instead, it should serve as an antidote to the tendency to become a prisoner of the ideological aspects enshrined in the very narratives used to give an account of the past.

The normative dimension of past accounts

“It is [...] possible to be prisoner of one’s own or others’ history, lived through or narrated [.. .] But human beings always have the possibility of liberating themselves from their histories, of reconstructing new versions of them and developing them towards an ending not totally determined by the past [.. .] Human beings confront the power that stories have on them by means of their power to recreate the stories they listen to or to invent new stories, thus exercising their autonomy” (Paolicchi, 2000, p. 302, my own translation from Spanish)

Symbolic mediation is related to agency since the use of signs and meaning-systems simultaneously enables and constrains our world view, our actions in it as well as our way of imagining other possible worlds (Bruner, 1986). As stated at the beginning, this mediational role of cultural artifacts is one of the main issues in which cultural psychology is interested. As Innis (2016) puts it, “cultural psychology studies [...] human conduct both controlled by and constituted by the use of signs, conduct elicited by and enforced by sign-configurations that for agents are simply ‘the way the world is,’ a form of semiotic reification” (p. 15). The latter is particularly true when it comes to memory, and especially to national and collective memory. As Wertsch (forthcoming) points out, national mnemonic communities have certain

memory habits which are built around different ways of emplotting events in accordance with particular storylines or narrative templates. These templates, transmitted in different social practices such as history teaching, “act as an unnoticed, yet very powerful ‘co-author’ when we attempt to simply tell what ‘really happened’ in the past” (Wertsch, 2007, p. 654). What is pictured here is a notion of agency distributed among individuals and the narrative templates provided by each national community, something that can easily result in different accounts of the past, sometimes fundamentally opposed to one other, thus giving rise to conflicts (Brescò & Wagoner, 2016).

As mentioned above, both psychology and history, as emerging scientific disciplines in the 19th century, have contributed to the construction of a normative framework for the subject of modernity in accordance with the needs of nation states. As for history, ever since it appeared in classrooms, it has been a tool used to transmit a shared past in order to encourage subjects to identify with their nation (Carretero, 2011), thus leading individuals to assume in first person plural both its past (its heroes and enemies, its affronts and claims) as well as its future challenges. Taking the Schank and Abelson model (1977) as a reference, we could say that history teaching has been, on occasion, equivalent to providing a kind of script, a script which, in narrating the past, also offers guidelines for interpreting the present state of certain conflicts, as well as directions for acting and positioning oneself in their regard. However, we cannot disregard the existence of other social memory practices besides history teaching. The past can be remembered both to legitimize certain political identities and structures and to claim historically marginalized identities (Misztal, 2003), to celebrate heroes and their victories, or to vindicate victims and speak on behalf of the defeated, to follow the example of our ancestors, or to learn from them and not repeat their mistakes. These practices are ultimately not exempt from a clear moral burden, the virtue of which depends on the end pursued in each specific context. For instance, remembering victims can be a virtue when there is a desire for justice to be done, but not when the intention is to stoke up old grievances and hatred among different collectives.

Following the decolonization period, the fall of the Soviet Bloc, and particularly, the current globalization process, we are finding ourselves up against a dynamic and heterogeneous scenario, marked by the presence of

countless meaning-systems competing to impose different world views, models of subjectivity as well as manifold ways of dealing with the past. In view of this scenario, I agree with Innis (2016) in that “cultural psychology [...] cannot be indifferent to human practices and should not consider them merely as exhibits in a kind of museum of curiosities” (p. 7). Far from it, cultural psychology, as a field centred on meaning-making and mediational processes, should play an important role in fostering reflexivity by bringing the symbolic forms through which we make sense of our lives and the world we live in to the fore. Likewise, by focusing on symbolic tools, such as narratives, and the specific practices of remembering in which these tools are used, we can gain a more reflective knowledge of how accounts of the past are constructed. This can certainly work against semiotic reification and thus contribute to gaining awareness of the symbolic tools used when remembering the past, or to paraphrase Bartlett (1932), “to acquire the capacity to turn around upon [one’s] own ‘schemata’ and construct them afresh” (p. 206). The whole point would be to enable individuals to go from being actors, subject to unnoticed, ready-made scripts, to being authors endowed with more agency to imagine new ways of looking at the past.

However, this is a task that is unlikely to be done individually. As Brinkmann (2016) rightly points out, human flourishing is necessarily bound to human inter-dependency, and more so in an increasingly globalized and multicultural world. In this sense, we agree with Rosa and González (2012) in that, in such a scenario, ethics of virtue call for account to be taken of the other, including the external other. Thus, far from being a threat, others are an indispensable element in order to reflect upon oneself and upon one’s own stories so that new ones can be co-constructed. This is because history, like poetry, is to a certain extent an art form aimed at imagining different possible worlds.

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, author-ship, and/or publication of this article.

Funding

The author(s) disclosed receipt of the following financial support for the research, author-ship, and/or publication of this article: The preparation of this

paper was supported by the Niels Bohr Professorship grant from the Grundforskningsfond of the Danish Ministry of Science and Technology.

References

- Anderson, B. (1983). *Imagined communities*. London: Verso.
- Bartlett, F. C. (1932). *Remembering: A study in experimental and social psychology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Billig, M. (1995). *Banal nationalism*. London: Sage.
- Brescó, I. (2008). Giving national form to the content of the past. A study of the narrative construction of historical events. *Journal of Psychology and Society*, 1(1), 1–14.
- Brescó, I., & Wagoner, B. (2016). Context in the cultural psychology of remembering. In C. Stone, & L. Bietti (Eds.), *Contextualizing human memory* (pp. 69–85). London: Routledge.
- Brinkmann, S. (2016). Cultural psychology and its values. *Culture & Psychology*, 22(3), 376–386.
- Brockmeier, J., & Harré, R. (2001). Narrative. problems and promises of an alternative paradigm. In J. Brockmeier, & D. Carbaugh (Eds.), *Narrative and identity: Studies in autobiography, self and culture* (pp. 39–58). Philadelphia: John Benjamins.
- Brown, S. D., & Reavey, P. (2015). *Vital memory and affect. Living with a difficult past*. London: Routledge.
- Bruner, J. (1986). *Actual minds, possible words*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Bruner, J., & Feldman, C. (1996). Group narrative as a cultural context of autobiography. In D. C. Rubin (Ed.), *Remembering our past* (pp. 291–317). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Burke, K. (1969). *Grammar of motives*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.
- Carretero, M. (2011). *Constructing patriotism: Teaching history and memories in global world*. Charlotte, NC: Information Age Publishing.
- Castro, J., Lafuente, E., & Jiménez, B. (2009). The soul of Spain: Spanish scholastic psychology and the making of modern subjectivity (1875–1931). *History of Psychology*, 12(3), 132–156.
- Castro, J., & Rosa, A. (2007). Psychology within time. Theorizing about the

- making of socio-cultural psychology. In J. Valsiner, & A. Rosa (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of sociocultural psychology* (pp. 62–80). New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Danto, A. C. (1985). *Narration and knowledge: Including the integral text of analytical philosophy of history*. New York, NY: Columbia University Press.
- Danziger, K. (2008). *Marking the mind. A history of memory*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Dewey (1938/1986). *Logic: The theory of inquiry*. Carbondale: Southern Illinois University Press.
- Egan, K. (1978). Thucydides, tragedian. In R. H. Canary, & H. Kozicki (Eds.), *The writing of history. Literary form and historical understanding* (pp. 63–92). Madison, WI: The University of Wisconsin Press.
- Gellner, E. (1983). *Nations and nationalism*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press.
- Gibbs, R. (1994). *The poetics of mind: Figurative thought, language, and understanding*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Hobsbawm, E. (1990). *Nations and nationalism since 1780: Programme, myth, reality*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Hutt, C. (2013). *John Dewey and the ethics of historical belief*. New York: State University of New York Press.
- Iggers, G., & von Moltke, K. (Eds.). (1973). *The theory and practice of history*. Indianapolis, IN: Bobbs-Merrill Co.
- Innis, R. E. (2016). Between philosophy and cultural psychology: Pragmatist and semiotic reflections on the thresholds of sense. *Culture & Psychology*, 22(3), 331–361.
- Jahoda, G. (1992). *Crossroads between culture and mind: Continuities and change in theories of human nature*. New York, NY: Harvester/Wheatsheaf.
- Kermode, F. (1966). *The sense of an ending*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Margalit, A. (2002). *The ethics of memory*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Mink, L. O. (1978). Narrative form as a cognitive instrument. In R. H.

- Canary, & H. Kozicki (Eds.), *The Writing of history. Literary form and historical understanding* (pp. 129–149). Madison, WI: The University of Wisconsin Press.
- Misztal, B. A. (2003). *Theories of social remembering*. Buckingham: Open University Press.
- Paolicchi, P. (2000). *Recordar y relatar*. In A. Rosa, G. Bellelli, & D. Bakhurst (Eds.), *Memoria colectiva e identidad nacional* (pp. 279–306). Biblioteca Nueva: Madrid.
- Polkinghorne, D. E. (1988). *Narrative knowing and the human sciences*. Albany: State University of New York Press.
- Ricoeur, P. (1981). *Narrative time*. In W. J. T. Mitchell (Ed.), *On narrative* (pp. 165–186). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Roberts, G. (2001). *The history and narrative debate, 1960–2000*. In G. Roberts (Ed.), *The history and narrative reader* (pp. 1–21). London: Routledge.
- Rosa, A. (2007). *Acts of psyche: Actuations as synthesis of semiosis and action*. In J. Valsiner, & A. Rosa (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of sociocultural psychology* (pp. 205–236). New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Rosa, A., & Brescó, I. (forthcoming). *What history to teach when the social pact shakes?* In M. Carretero, S. Berger, & M. Grever (Eds.), *International handbook of research in historical cultural and history education* London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Rosa, A., & González F. (2012). *Citizenship, virtues and self in multicultural societies. A view of the embodiment of values in the developing self*. In A. Branco, & J. Valsiner (Eds.), *Cultural psychology of human values* (pp. 3–29). Charlotte, NC: Information Age Publications.
- Rose, N. (1985). *The psychological complex*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- Schacter, D. (2001). *The seven sins of memory*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
- Schank, R. C., & Abelson, R. P. (1977). *Scripts, plans, goals, and understanding*. Hillsdale, NJ: LEA.
- Vygotsky, L. (1987). *The collected works of L.S. Vygotsky. Volume 4: The history of the development of higher mental functions*. NY: Plenum Press.
- Weinrich, H. (2004). *Lethe. The art and critique of forgetting*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press.

- Wertsch, J. V. (forthcoming). National memory and where to find it. In B. Wagoner (Ed.), *Handbook of culture and memory*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Wertsch, J. V. (2007). Collective memory. In J. Valsiner, & A. Rosa (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of sociocultural psychology* (pp. 645–660). New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Wertsch, J. V. (2006). *Voices of collective remembering*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- White, H. (1973). *Metahistory: The historical imagination in nineteenth-century Europe*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- White, H. (1978). The history text as literary artifact. In R. H. Canary, & H. Kozicki (Eds.), *The writing of history. Literary form and historical understanding* (pp. 41–62). Madison, WI: The University of Wisconsin Press.
- White, H. (1986). *The content of the form*. Baltimore: The Johns Hopkins University Press.